

AN ANALYSIS OF THE NEUTRALISATION CURVES OF THE COLLOIDAL ACIDS. PART V

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The nature of the deviations in many of the experimental curves from the theoretical curves presented earlier (Parts I-IV) has been pointed out and probable reasons discussed. The deviations may be caused by the non-accessibility of the micellar positions at a low p_H to the cations of the titrating base as well as by changes in the state of aggregation during titration.

In our previous communications (Parts I-IV, this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 587; 1957, 34, 63, 691, 696) we proposed a model for the acid colloidal particles and several equations based on the model, to represent their neutralisation curves, with experimental verifications. The literature on this subject, however, contains curves of widely varying shapes, and any attempt to fit the formulae with any such curve is very likely to meet with frustration. The curves published in Parts I-IV (*loc. cit.*) were chosen curves from the literature and were discovered after repeated failures to reach agreement between calculated and experimental values in different similar curves. This is due to the fact that only a selected number of titrations have been conducted in such a way that the existing conditions are favourable for the assumptions to hold good and the equations to apply.

The present communication aims at presenting qualitatively the reasons for the observed deviations in many of the experimental curves from the theoretical curves, presented earlier. The deviations may be caused by two entirely different processes (Cases D and E), which are described below, mostly with reference to clay systems containing weakly acidic groups like $-\text{SiOH}$ and $-\text{AlOH}$ groups, which have been widely studied.

Case D.—A broad survey of the literature for the titration curves of the clay minerals reveals that two types of curves have generally been obtained in different laboratories, neglecting minor variations. Both the types are known for the same type of material, viz., titration of a bentonite (legend Rock River) by Bradfield (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1930, 34, 360), and titration of a bentonite (legend Wyoming) by Marshall ("Colloid Chemistry of the Silicate Minerals", 1949). The former starts apparently as a strong acid, passes through an inflection and then ends as a weak acid (Curve A, Fig. 1), resembling the curves we have discussed so far and may be analysed analogously. The second type of curve (Curve B, Fig. 1) shows an initial moderately weak acid feature, a flat run at a comparatively high p_H , an inflection and finally a very weak acid feature. This type of curve is not covered by the considerations made earlier. We can, of course, provide a qualitative explanation for this kind of behaviour from our model. It is likely that the closeness of lattice along c -axis in the Wyoming bentonite in its H-form, or, the comparatively short distance of inter-particle separation in an aggregate that encloses the micellar H^+ ions in general,

does not allow Na^+ ions, which are hydrated to a large degree, to enter unless some degree of swelling has taken place, increasing the long spacing or the distance. This is achieved by the first addition of NaOH which neutralises the intermicellar acidity in the same way as any weak acid, raising the p_{H} and charging up the intermicellar surface by further ionisation from the intermicellar groups. This process serves to swell the aggregates or increase the interlayer distance of separation when the Na^+ ions begin to enter the micellar positions displacing the H^+ ions present there and the flat run of the titration curve is obtained at a higher p_{H} . The inflection indicates the saturation of the micellar positions and the weak polybasic acid neutralisation of the intermicellar groups again makes its appearance after the inflection.

FIG. 1

$a_{\text{Na}^+} - C_{\text{NaOH}}$ curves.—Marshall has developed clay membrane electrodes with which he has measured the activities of the free ions during a titration. His curves have a general feature, neglecting minor variations, as depicted in curve B' in Fig. 1 (Marshall, *loc. cit.*). The equations (6), (10) and (11) in Part I (*loc. cit.*) contain terms involving $(a_{\text{Na}^+})_i$ and each of them can be reduced to

$$b = C_a + z - \frac{C_a \cdot x}{x + z} \quad \text{where } z = (a_{\text{Na}^+})_i$$

or

$$b = \frac{C_a \cdot z}{z + x} + z \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

the nature of the curve to which equation between 'b' and 'z' is shown in Curve A' Fig. 1. This equation is independent of the dissociation constants at different stages

of neutralisation except for the values of 'x', i.e., independent of the nature of the intermicellar groups, weak or strong. At high p_x values $z \gg x$, i.e., $x + z \approx z$ and the equation reduces to

$$b = C_a + z \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

This means that the slope of the curve at high p_x is a straight line intercepting the abscissa at an angle of 45° , giving the value of C_a or the micellar acidity or the concentration of adsorbed ions. Our calculations are based on the assumption that the corresponding potentiometric curve is one given by Curve A, Fig. 1. The same hysteresis observed in the potentiometric curves of Marshall is also reflected here. In the case of a titration of Amberlite IR 120 with KOH, where the potentiometric curve is of the type A, the corresponding $ax^+ - C_{XOH}$ curve simulates curve A' (Marshall and Upchurch, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1953, 57, 618; Gupta, Part III, *loc. cit.*, Fig. 2.). It can be shown that for bivalent cations of the titrating base, reaction (2) will be $b = C_a + 2z$, and the limiting slope will be $26^\circ-34'$.

The Model and the Double Layer.—The equations and the experimental fits (Parts I-IV, *loc. cit.*) seem to justify our previous assumptions and the model. As regards the mechanism of ion adsorption, it is generally claimed that the adsorption takes place in the Stern's layer or there is ion-pair formation; but there is one difficulty in adopting such a hypothesis. The S-shaped curves indicate that the ions are first adsorbed and the charge on the surface increases subsequently due to ionisation, as is shown by the buffering after the inflection in the acid range when ion adsorption is almost complete and a limiting value is reached. The adsorption in Stern's layer or ion-pair formation mechanism at a free surface, on the other hand, requires first a large amount of ionisation from the surface and then adsorption due to a large increase of surface charge as in Curve B (Fig. 1); but this hypothesis cannot explain the subsequent buffering after inflection in that curve without assuming OH^- ion adsorption in that stretch (Marshall, *loc. cit.*). As the curves of the type A (Fig. 1) also exist, the location of the adsorption sites, which are present from the beginning of the titration, must be sought on a geometrical basis. Our model therefore allows only the formation of the Gouy-Chapman type of double layer. We do not think that ions, other than potential-determining ions like H^+ ions in the case of colloidal acids, or, Ag^+ and I^- ions in the case of AgI sols, can be adsorbed at a free surface. The phenomenon of charge reversal brought about by ions of higher valency type is often thought of as a proof of the existence of Stern's layer, but the same can be shown from our model as well. If a bivalent ion replaces two of the adsorbed or the micellar monovalent ions in the clay (Fig. 2), then we get a normal exchange, but if the monovalent ions are replaced, ion for ion, by the bivalent ions, then the particle as a whole gets oppositely charged and we get a charge reversal. This is quite akin to the replacement of tetravalent Si by trivalent Al atom or replacement of trivalent Al by divalent Mg atom in the clay lattice that produces the charge. The same argument applies to the resin system or any other system.

Case E.—The second type of deviation from the theoretical curves can be understood from a consideration of the fundamental assumptions involved in the postulation

of the model and of the theoretical curves. It has been assumed that the location of the adsorption sites, and as such the adsorption capacity or the micellar acidity, C_a , depends upon the number and geometry of the aggregates, and during a titration the number of such aggregates or in other words, the particle size distribution, remains fixed. Large changes in the shape of the titration curves can be produced by changes in the state of aggregation in a given suspension during titration. If the particles in a given suspension gradually adhere together, as by a process of aggregation or coagulation, it will mean creation of new adsorption sites with each adherence. On the other hand, if an aggregate breaks up, some of the adsorption sites vanish and become intermicellar groups (cf. the magnified aggregate in Fig. 2). It was shown earlier that the effect of ion adsorption due to the Donnan equilibrium was to produce a flattening in the neutralisation curve ($b - p_H$). Also creation of new adsorption sites means a diminution in the activities of the free ions, i.e., $(a_M)_f$, whatever may be the valency of M , and a corresponding decrease in the specific conductivity (κ). The curves for the variation of p_H , the specific conductivity and $(a_M)_f$ with concentration of added base, i.e., 'b', are related and the change in one is bound to be reflected in the other curves. It will be seen from the literature cited below that the bivalent cations are the worse offenders in disturbing the state of aggregation of a colloidal suspension and producing the deviations, assuming of course that the bases containing trivalent cations are not used for titration. In this connection we may refer to Mattson's observation that the size of a clay particle depends upon the exchangeable ion in the clay and is bigger in the case of Ca-clay than in the case of Li- or Na-clay (*Soil Sci.*, 1929, 28, 373). Suspensions are, in general, more or less tolerant to small concentrations of the monovalent cations of the titrating base without producing any aggregating or disaggregating changes. Fig. 2(a) shows schematically, in two

FIG. 2

dimensions, plate-shaped particles in a colloidal suspension with occasional aggregates; which state is usually maintained when a titration proceeds with caustic alkali. The suspension has a small micellar acidity due to the presence of the few aggregates and a large amount of intermicellar acidity. If the existing aggregates remain firm and no further aggregation takes place, the theoretical curve (Curve A, Fig. 3) will be obtained which will correspond to our derived equations (equations 11 and 12; Part I, *loc. cit.*). If with the addition of the base a slow process of aggregation takes place throughout the titration, there will be a gradual flattening of the neutralisation curve as shown in Curve B, Fig. 3, the suspension in the meanwhile passing from stage (a) to stage (b) or (c) in Fig. 2 (cf. Mukherjee and Mitra, *J. Coll. Sci.*, 1946, 1, 141, Fig. 6). If there is a rapid aggregation at the beginning and no further aggregation subsequently, then the slope of the curve will correspond to Curve C, Fig. 3. This means the suspension has attained stages (b) or (c) only for a small addition of the base and no further aggregation is taking place afterwards.

FIG. 3

The slope of these curves after inflection is again theoretical (cf. Mukherjee *et al.*, *Trans. Nat. Inst. Sci. India*, 1937, 1, 227, Fig. 20; Mukherjee and Mitra, *loc. cit.*, Fig. 7). If the aggregation is rapid at the beginning and a slow process of aggregation continues after the inflection, it will lead to a curve, Curve D, Fig. 3 [cf. Part II, *loc. cit.*, Fig. 1, Ba(OH)₂ titration curve]. This means the stage (a)

to (b) is rapid while a slow process leads to stage (c) in Fig. 2. The corresponding expected $b-\kappa$ curves are shown by Curves A', B', C' and D', and the $b-a_M$ curves by A'', B'', C'' and D'' respectively in Fig. 3. This means all the curves are depressed by corresponding amounts. A combination of the above results with that described in Case D, may lead to curves E and F and corresponding $b-\kappa$ curves to E' and F', and $b-a_M$ to curves E'' and F'' (cf. curves published by Chatterjee and Marshall, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1950, 54, 671). If due to the addition of the titrating base, disaggregation or peptisation occurs, the changes will take place in the opposite direction. These results follow from our assumption regarding the adsorption sites. The curves B and C also show how intersecting curves are possible in these systems (cf. Mukherjee and Mitra, *loc. cit.*, Fig. 8). Again, aggregation at one stage of the titration and disaggregation at some other stage, or, aggregation by instalments may give rise to oscillations and inflections in a curve leading one to the erroneous conclusion that the colloidal acid concerned is dibasic or tribasic for that reason (cf. Mukherjee and Mitra, *loc. cit.*, Fig. 9., and curve 3, Fig. 10.). The real dibasic or tribasic features can only be understood from the structure of the colloidal particles and from the consideration of the nature of the intermicellar active groups. The above considerations also show why a large amount of base is required to reach the inflection point in presence of salts which are good coagulating or aggregating agents. As different cations have different aggregating powers, the influence of the lyotropic series on these curves is only obvious (cf. Mukherjee and Mitra, *loc. cit.*, Figs. 6 and 8). The effect of aggregation in all cases is to increase the value of C_a , or the micellar acidity and the effect of peptisation is to diminish the value of C_a . The base-exchange capacity in clays, which is roughly denoted by C_a is thus not a fixed quantity for the same sample and depends on the number and type of structures of the aggregates formed and is thus different for different reagents at different concentrations of a reagent and at different p_a .

The formation of gel structure by the agglomeration of sol particles has been reported by Bernal (*Trans. Faraday Soc. Disc.*, 1945, 42B, 1). Incidentally, the aggregates in (c) in Fig. 2, suggest schematically how the formation of tactoids is possible with increasing concentration of sol particles.

It should be noted that the stages (a), (b) and (c) in Fig. 2 do not signify anything else beyond showing schematically increasing degree of aggregation.

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In Parts III & IV (this *Journal*, 1957, 35, 691-701), p. 695, line 11, please read PMR for PQR; p. 699, line 1, read

$$b - C_i - \frac{K_w}{x} + x \text{ for } b - C_i = \frac{K_w}{x} + x;$$

Some page line 17 from bottom; read $\bar{V}_{Na^+}$ and a_{Na^+} for $2\bar{V}_{Na^+}$ and $2a_{Na^+}$; p. 700 line 12, read (a_{OH^-}) for $2(a_{OH^-})$.